

IMAGINATION

Rakhimova Feruza

is a teacher of the Kokon State Pedagogical Institute.

Artikova Mubinabanu

Kadirova Shohistabonu

1st year students of the Faculty of National Handicrafts
and Applied Arts of the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute.

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Annotation: the article provides information about the processes of psychological imagination.

Key words: Imagination, Passive imagination, voluntary, involuntary imagination.

We will encounter another unique phenomenon of the human psyche by studying the ability of a person to create something new - a quality that is unique to any creature living on the planet Earth. Its essence is to create an image in a person's mind that does not yet exist in reality, and the basis for creating such an image is the past experience.

Imagination is a process of reorganizing impressions that reflect reality and creating new impressions based on this. Imagination is a psychological process of creating something new in the form of an image, imagination or idea. Images of imagination differ from images of perception and images of memory in that they are defined and in this order that a person has not yet encountered. These are events, proofs, events that have not happened before human eyes and cannot happen. One can expect events and incidents that are expected to happen in imaginary images. The formation of imaginary images can be realized only at a high level of human mental development.

Physiological basis of imagination consists in actualization of nerve connections, their destruction, regrouping and merging into new systems, formation of new harmonies of temporary connections formed in the past experience. In this case, the simple updating of existing temporary connections does not lead to the creation of newness. The creation of newness is the harmony created by temporary nerve connections that were not previously harmonized with each other. The imagination process consists of the cooperative activity of both communication systems. In this case, the second message system - the word - is of great importance. All visual images are continuously connected with it. The word serves as a source of formation of imaginary images, controls the way of finding their content, is a means of preserving, strengthening and changing

them. Imagination is always a departure from reality, but in any situation the source of imagination is objective reality.

2). Imagination has performed a number of special tasks in human life:

1. It consists in being able to express reality in images and use them in solving problems. This function of the imagination is related to thinking and is organically incorporated into it.

2. It consists of managing emotional states. With the help of his imagination, a person will be able to satisfy many needs and reduce the stress caused by it.

3. Imagination is related to the participation of human cognitive processes and states, in particular, perception, attention, memory, speech and voluntary control of emotions. Through images, a person has the opportunity to control perception, memories, expressions.

4. The formation of the internal plan of action consists of the ability to perform them in the mind using images.

5. Planning and programming of activities, creation of such programs, evaluation of their effectiveness, implementation process.

Imagination plays a very important role in human life. It is almost impossible to do any labor activity without the participation of the imagination. For example, in order to make something, to grow a plant, it is necessary to know the results in advance, that is, to imagine them in the imagination. Therefore, imagination is a component of many activities. When a person is in a difficult situation, when he cannot solve a problem, when he tries to avoid his mistakes, he can enter into useless dreams, into the world of fiction far from real life. This type of imagination is called Passive. Passive imagination can occur voluntarily or involuntarily. A type of passive fantasy that is voluntarily created, but does not lead to life, activity in real life, is called sweet fantasy. It is common for everyone to indulge in sweet dreams about some happy, pleasant things. But if there are more cases of sweet dreams in a person's life, this is a sign of a person's passivity. Passive imagination can occur involuntarily. This type of illusion mainly occurs when the activity of the mind, the second signal system decreases, when a person is in a temporary state of inactivity, in a state of drowsiness, in a state of affect, during sleep (dreaming), when the mind is disturbed due to illness (hallucination) and so on. Active imagination, which is the opposite of passive imagination, is divided into creative and restorative imagination. Imagination that creates a system of corresponding images on the basis of a certain basis, writings, drawings is called regenerative imagination.

Creative imagination is the creation of new images that are realized in original and valuable material products, as opposed to regenerative imagination. Creative IMAGINATION is an integral part of all types of technical, artistic and other creativity.

Creative imagination is to describe something new for a certain person in words or imagine it based on conditional reflection (drawing, notation, etc.). This type of imagination is widely used in various activities of a person, at the same time, in education.

Imagination processes. How are fantasy images created?

Imagination processes are also analytical and synthetic in nature, like perception, memory, thinking. Analysis provides an opportunity to separate and preserve some general features of an object, such as perception and memory, and to avoid unimportant features. As a result of the analysis and subsequent synthesis, a template is created. Based on this standard, the external world, existence, subjects and events are studied. Analysis and synthesis have a different place and direction in the process of imagination. Of course, the consistency between the new and the old is preserved. In the processes of imagination, the synthesis of imagination is carried out in different ways.

Agglutination is an imaginative process that consists of "gluing together" various qualities, features and parts that cannot be combined in our everyday life. Through agglutination, more fairy tale images are created (a mermaid, a house standing on chicken legs, a centaur, and so on). etc.) Agglutination is also used in technical creation. (tank, amphibian, seaplane).

HYPERBOLIZATION - creating new images by enlarging and reducing things, increasing the number of their parts, replacing them.

SCHEMATIZATION (schematization) - taking a template from an existing object and creating images based on this template. For example, artists create things based on the image of various plants.

3). The individual characteristics of the imagination are expressed in the differentiation according to the level of development of the human imagination and the type of images that are used more often. The level of development of the imagination was characterized by the vividness and depth of images processing of past experience data, as well as the novelty and understanding of the results of this processing. The power and fullness of the imagination can be easily appreciated in the authors of unreal and miraculous images of the product of imagination, for example, magical tales. Weakness of imagination development is expressed by the processing of imagination at a lower level. Weakness of

imagination development causes difficulties in solving logical problems that require the ability to visually imagine a certain situation. It is impossible to live an emotionally rich and comprehensive life when the imagination is not sufficiently developed.

A person is not born with a developed imagination. Its development takes place during ontogenesis and requires the accumulation of a reserve of imagination that serves as material for the creation of imaginary images. Imagination develops in the process of education, as well as with thinking, memory, will and intuition, in an organic relationship with the development of the individual. The first expression of the imagination is inextricably linked with the process of perception. It becomes invisible when he begins to process the impressions he received in his games by changing them in his imagination. A chair becomes an airplane, a box becomes a car. An important stage in the development of imagination is related to the age when a child acquires speech.

All great scientists and inventors had powerful and widely developed imaginations. For example, let's take the realization of the ancient dream of mankind. The idea of flying in the air appeared to people thousands of years ago. Among the ancient Egyptians there are pictures and statues of people with wings. The same images appeared later among the Greeks and Romans. The same desire is reflected in the legends of the peoples of the world. For example, there is a flying carpet in Russian and Middle Eastern fairy tales. It is no exaggeration to say that these dreams are the impetus for human conquest of space.

Conclusion: without imagination, everything around is dull, like a colorless movie, and when a global cataclysm occurs, as it is today, and they have nothing to imagine tomorrow, excess stress arises. it weakens the nervous system, lowers immunity. They become an easy victim of any external influence, including infection. We rule the world, because other animals only believe in things that exist in the imagination - God, the state, money or human rights, imagination and dreams is not able to believe. Without imagination, there is no creativity, so there is no culture, because the main tool of culture - art is impossible without creative imagination. Freud defined culture as "a way of existence that mankind chooses to preserve in order to preserve itself". Culture unites society, limits our ever-increasing hatred. It is impossible to live in society without culture.

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